

MODELLING THE POTENTIAL OF HEAT RECOVERY FROM UK HOUSING DEVELOPMENTS

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Nomenclature

h_{wa}	Coefficient of heat exchange from water to air
h_{ws}	Coefficient of heat exchange from water to soil
Q_{PR}	Potentially recoverable heat
P_W	Wetted perimeter
P_u	Unwetted perimeter
P_w	Wetted perimeter
R_{wa}	Thermal resistivity from water to air
R_{ws}	Thermal resistivity from water to soil
T_a	Temperature of sewer air
T_s	Ambient temperature of soil
d_p	Diameter of pipe wall
n_M	Manning friction coefficient
q_{wa}	Heat transfer from wastewater to sewer air per unit length
q_{ws}	Heat transfer from wastewater to soil per unit length
u_a	Average velocity of sewer air
u_w	Average velocity of wastewater
h	Depth of wastewater in sewer
kWh	Kilowatt hours
LPM	Litres per minute
LPS	Litres per second
SD	Standard deviation
WWHR	Wastewater heat recovery
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant
A	Cross sectional area of flow
B	Breadth of wastewater free surface
D	Inner pipe diameter
F	Flowrate
R	Roughness
S	Slope of channel
T	Temperature

Declaration

Authorship Declaration

I certify that I have read and understood the entry in the Programme Handbook for the Department of Chemical Engineering on Cheating and Plagiarism and that all material in this report is my own work, except where I have indicated with appropriate references or acknowledgements. I agree that, in line with Regulation 15.3(e), if requested I will submit an electronic copy of this work for submission to a Plagiarism Detection Service for quality assurance purposes.

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Abstract

81.5% of domestic energy consumption is used in heating and to meet decarbonisation targets alternative low carbon energy sources must be exploited (ONS, 2021). Heat from domestic wastewater is a source of low carbon energy but it can be difficult to identify viable sites for in-sewer heat recovery. In an attempt to build tools for easy assessment of viability, the UK Time Usage Survey was used to build UK diurnal patterns for major demographics which were then implemented in the SIMDEUM stochastic model for wastewater profile generation. These wastewater profiles were imported to an EPA storm water management sewer network model of a 113 home new housing development for testing. Flowrates adhered to expected diurnal patterns, but total flow was only 58-70% of expected national levels. In-sewer temperatures were successfully modelled by treating heat as a material pollutant, and options for modelling temperature loss using pollutant removal functions were explored. The development did not meet the 10l/s dry weather flowrate suggested for heat recovery, but if values are corrected upwards then low power 10kW systems may be viable.

1. Introduction

The UK has committed itself to net zero carbon emissions by 2050 requiring increases in energy efficiency and energy production from renewable resources (CST, 2020). In 2019, 64.5% of domestic energy consumption in the UK was used for space heating while 17.0% was used for water heating (ONS, 2021), so decarbonisation of heating is an important opportunity.

In the UK 1.21 billion litres of domestic wastewater are discharged into sewers every day under dry flow conditions with an average temperature of 17.5C (Ali and Gillich, 2019). Due to high the heat capacity of water, if 3C of cooling could be used for WWHR it would be possible to generate 1.5TWh of heat energy annually (ibid.) which would be 1.2% of total UK renewable energy generation in 2019 (ONS, 2020).

Due to the low grade of heat collected through WWHR, transforming it into electricity is not a viable option and it is instead used for heating. When collected outside of the home this energy is instead better used in a heat network/district heating which directly delivers hot water to a heat exchanger inside domestic buildings through a network of pipes (DBEIS, 2018). Due to the large percentage of domestic energy consumption which is used for heating the UK government does not believe that it will be able to meet its 2050 decarbonisation target unless at least 18% of UK heat is distributed by heat networks from sources such as WWHR (DBEIS, 2021). To this end the UK government is providing £320m of investments and other incentives to support heat networks, making identifying locations at which WWHR may be implemented a priority (ibid.).

There are three potential locations at which WWHR may be implemented in the residential context: inside individual households (in-drain), in the sewers those households discharge to (in-sewer), and in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) responsible for handling the effluent. In-drain WWHR is advantageous in that it requires the smallest minimum capital investment and that it recovers energy where temperatures are both highest and closest to the point of demand, but it is limited by the intermittent nature of the wastewater flowrate that makes energy less likely to be available when needed without investment in storage capacity (Pinter and Durou, 2020) While all WWHR must deal with high amounts of fouling, in-drain systems attached to cleaner units like showers may be less vulnerable and cleaned more regularly as part of household maintenance (ibid.). Conversely, recovery at WWTP has a high and consistent flow of wastewater as well as better fouling characteristics due to the removal of biological material (Elias-Maxil et al., 2014) but suffers from being far away from domestic

demand for energy and a lower average temperature of wastewater. In-sewer WWHR is predictably the intermediate position between in-drain and at WWTP, as summarised in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1 Overview of WWHR Location Properties					
Location	Temperature	Flow Characteristics	Fouling	Proximity to User	Capital
In-Drain	High	Low, intermittent	Lower*	Immediate	Low
In-Sewer	Intermediate	Intermediate	Higher	Near	Intermediate
At WWTP	Low	High, consistent	Lower	Far	High

While the technology required for recovering heat from sewers is well understood there are still many practical considerations including maintenance and economic viability which remain unclear, and it has not yet been implemented in the United Kingdom. The aim of this study has therefore been **to develop tools that may assist in evaluating the viability of in-sewer WWHR in residential areas. To do this it must be possible to easily determine the flow and temperature patterns of wastewater within the sewer network to estimate the energy available for recovery and the suitability of different recovery technologies.** Elias-Maxil (2015) developed a system for determining the temperature profile of domestic wastewater but while this report owes a great deal to their thesis many of the tools they developed depend on proprietary software which limits accessibility.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Heat Recovery Technologies

There are already a number of commercially available WWHR systems that could be installed in gravity sewers. These fall into two broad categories: systems that line the walls of the sewer pipes and systems that pump filtered sewer water above ground into a separate heat exchanger unit (Dürrenmatt and Wanner, 2014). In the latter case there are additional costs involved in pumping and wastewater must be filtered before pumping to minimise blockages in the heat exchanger due to debris, but by having a more compact heat exchange unit in a more accessible location it is possible to clean the unit and minimise fouling (ibid.). Figure 2.1.1 below shows the basic units of these two kinds of WWHR systems.

Figure 2.1.1 Two principle modes of in-sewer domestic WWHR, adapted from Vestberg (2017).

Three types of exchanger used in above ground applications: shell and tube, plate, and spiral. Shell and tube exchangers require the most maintenance and are most expensive, but give the best performance (Mazhar, Liu, and Shukla, 2018). Plate heat exchangers require the least maintenance, produce lower pressure drops than other methods and are somewhat modular meaning that scaling the device for the local demand is easier, but the performance is not as good (ibid.). Spiral heat exchangers are rarely used for WWHR applications but are often used

in WWTP to handle sludge due to the turbulent self-cleaning flows which they induce (Lines, 2014).

In-sewer heat exchange systems can be divided into two categories: liners that can be installed in pre-existing sewer networks and systems that are fully integrated into sewer pipes. Figures 2.1.2 and 2.1.3 below show commercially available examples of each.

<p>Figure 2.1.2 Uhrig Therm-liner system installed in established sewers (Unitracc, 2011).</p>	<p>Figure 2.1.3 Rabtherm integrated heat exchangers ready for installation (Rabtherm, 2007).</p>

Commercially available systems require high dry weather flowrates to be economically viable by the admission of their manufacturers, with minimum flow requirements ranging from 600-1500LPM (Ostapczk and Railsback, 2013).

Heat pumps are used in WWHR systems to draw heat from wastewater at relatively low temperatures and transfer it to media with higher temperatures. The coefficient of performance (COP) defined below in equation 2.1.1 is used to evaluate heat pumps according to how much additional work needs to be put into the system to reclaim the extracted heat (Arnell, Lund, and Jeppson, 2017)

$$COP = \frac{\text{Useful heat extracted}}{\text{Work energy put into system}} \tag{2.1.1}$$

The COP for WWHR systems varies not only according to design but also the specific temperatures of wastewater and on the heat pump side (ibid.) but are usually found to be between 3-4 (Ali and Gillich, 2019). However, in some pilot and small scale systems COP as high as 7 have been recorded in operation (ibid.).

In any heat exchange system some fouling is to be expected, but the nature of wastewater and the sewer environment makes fouling a significant concern. Elias-Maxil et al. (2014) reported that 30% reductions in heat transfer efficiency due to the biological fouling were commonly found in WWHR systems, and many systems are oversized in an attempt to compensate for these losses. Other costs are incurred in systems where wastewater is pumped through a heat exchanger due to biofilm constricting flow and increasing the work required to pump (ibid.). For heat exchange systems that line sewer pipes in combined sewer networks heat transfer will also be affected by inorganic sediment deposits from surface runoff which may not be removed by cleaning processes targeted at removing biological fouling and less dense deposits (ibid.).

As the biological processes responsible for much of wastewater treatment broadly follow Arrhenius' law within the range of temperatures tolerable to the microorganisms, there are concerns that in-sewer heat recovery could have a negative impact on downstream processes (Ceconet et al., 2020). For example, Wanner et al. (2015) found that a permanent 1°C reduction in influent temperature would result in 10% reduction of maximum net specific growth rate for nitrifying microorganisms and subsequently would necessitate a 10% increase in sludge tank size. For these reasons some countries such as Germany have legal requirements to limit wastewater cooling to 0.5°C before WWTPs (Elias-Maxil, 2015, p.20). However, as temperature losses occur naturally within sewer pipes and as cooling processes generally follow an exponential decay function it is obvious how in-sewer heat recovery near points of discharge into sewers will affect the influent of WWTP that are potentially many miles downstream. In Ceconet et al.'s (2020) study on a Czech heat recovery scheme the final effect on influent temperatures was found to be only -0.056°C in winter conditions and +0.045°C in summer conditions when heat pumps were used for cooling, but this was only for one building pulling 188,000kWh/yr and they noted the potential for downstream issues to arise in the case of wider adoption.

However, there may be additional benefits to removing heat from wastewater as the fat, oil, and grease (FOG) deposits that contribute to sewer blockages and overflows are formed through hydrolysis and saponification processes rather than simple cooling as is commonly believed (Iasmin, Dean and Ducoste, 2016). As these processes are driven by temperature, temperature reductions could reduce the deposition of FOG as well as general pipe corrosion due to H₂S (Abdel-Aal et al. 2019).

Another barrier to the adoption of in-sewer WWHR technologies is the high minimum flow requirement at the point of heat extraction (Elias-Maxil, 2015, p.21). In-sewer WWHR also requires that heat be recovered near to its eventual consumer for it to be economically viable, with Ali and Gillich (2019) giving 500m as the maximum practical distance. These factors combined make the complexity of determining the potential of WWHR itself an obstacle to adoption, with many reports on feasibility simply concluding that it is dependent on many factors and that long term studies on potential sites are required (Vestberg, 2017).

2.2 Heat Storage Technologies

As heat recovery is not synchronised with demand for heat and follows a diurnal pattern that lags behind the pattern of discharge into sewers, systems which allow for recovered heat to be stored increase the value of WWHR systems (Ali and Gillich, 2019). This is done by creating a body of warmer or cooler matter that can be used as heat source or coolant later, as other energy storage technologies such as latent heat storage and chemical energy storage are not economical with the large quantities of low grade heat obtained through WWHR (Welsch et al., 2018).

Ironically, water is a good medium for thermal energy storage for the same reason it is worth trying to recover low grade heat from wastewater: it has a high density, high heat capacity, and can be pumped. Water can be used to store heat either in a well-insulated tank or in underground aquifers (Elias-Maxil, 2015). Figure 2.2.1 below shows the basic operation of aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES) systems, making use of both a hot and a cold well.

Figure 2.2.1 Aquifer thermal energy storage operation from Schuppler, Fleuchaus, and Blum (2019)

When there is demand for cooling, cold water is pumped from the cool well and used in heat pumps or direct heat exchange after which it is injected into the warm water well at an elevated temperature (Schuppler, Fleuchaus, and Blum, 2019). When there is demand for heating, warm water is drawn from the hot well, used in heat pumps, and injected into the cool well at a lower temperature (ibid.). Depending on demand for either heating or cooling, water that has had its temperature changed by heat pumps during WWHR can be added to either well for long term storage, although in a domestic context in Northern Europe heating demand is likely to always outstrip cooling demand (ibid.). ATES is limited by the need for natural aquifers with high hydraulic conductivity, preferably with impermeable layers above and below the aquifer, and favourable water chemistry at high temperatures to minimise fouling at exchanger elements (Novo et al., 2010).

An underground alternative to aquifer thermal energy storage is borehole thermal energy storage (BTES) which uses a series of heat exchangers to supply both heating and cooling from a single well, requiring greater investment due to the increased mechanical complexity (Elias-Maxil et al., 2014). Sizing BTES systems can be difficult because the condition of soil which determines heat capacity varies with location and ground moisture content, but typically they require 3-5 times the volume of storage systems that use water for primary storage (Xu, Wang, and Li, 2014).

In Figure 2.2.2 below, Calder (2016) provides an illustration of how long term and short-term storage methods might be combined to provide useful heat from WWHR and BTES, using an intermediary water storage system to overcome the lower heat transfer rate of soil noted by Xu, Wang, and Li (2014).

Figure 2.2.2 Combined WWHR and BTES system from Calder (2016).

3. The Site

The site chosen for analysis was the first phase of the Brabazon development near Bristol in South West England. The developers are interested in supporting sustainable living, including reductions in carbon footprint (YTL Developments, 2020, p.10), which makes the development worthy of consideration and the new sewer network would make installation of WWHR systems less problematic than with older sites. Figure 3.1 below shows a map of the first phase of development housing with its sewer network super imposed, which includes 80 houses and a tower block containing 33 apartments.

Figure 3.2 below shows a more accurate map of the sewer network, with the network outfall marked by an inverted triangle.

By reading the map of the sewer network it was established that the path of flow through the sewer network to the network outfall was no more than 250m for any node, and the maximum direct distance between the outfall and a network node was 168m. This satisfies the proximity requirements for WWHR suggested by Ali and Gillich (2019), making the site suitable for assessment.

4. Theory of Model

The site was to be modelled by combining pre-existing tools to generate water temperature and discharge patterns on a per house basis. These household discharge patterns could then be connected to a model of the sewer network.

4.1 Simulation of Water Demand, End-Use Model

KWR's "Simulation of Water Demand, End-Use Model" (SIMDEUM) is a stochastic model of water use and discharge patterns (Pieterse-Quirijns, 2014, p.7) at the household level. For a given building it generates a random number of occupants based on demographic data and determines whether they are awake and present in the building based on the diurnal patterns for the occupant's demographic cohort. Each building is assigned a number of water appliances based on an associated percentage for that building type, and if an occupant is both present and awake there is a chance that they might use an appliance based on the average frequency of use for that demographic. Additionally, SIMDEUM distinguishes between different uses for the same appliance so that bathroom taps may be used either to wash hands or to shave, producing different discharge volumes and temperatures accordingly.

For the purposes of assessing the viability of WWHR, stochastic modelling of discharge has an advantage over continuous models in that it may highlight where irregularities in wastewater flowrate may undermine performance of recovery equipment. For example, if there was only one house with a single occupant discharging into a system, whatever the average flowrate might be across a 24-hour period the modal flowrate would presumably be 0 LPM.

4.2 Storm Water Management Model

The EPA storm water management Model (SWMM) is primarily used to determine the impact of wet weather events on the urban water cycle with special consideration for combined sewer systems where wet weather events can create flooding events.

For the purposes of a modelling a closed gravity sewer the network consists of inflow nodes, junction nodes, outfalls, and channels. At inflow nodes wastewater is added to the network as described by a time series. At junction nodes flows are combined and are proceed onwards as a perfectly mixed plug. The outfall is simply the last node in the network where wastewater is removed. Channels carry wastewater along their length between nodes according to the Manning equation (4.2.1) given below

$$F = \frac{1.49}{n_M} AR^{2/3} S^{1/2} \quad (4.2.1)$$

where F is the flow rate, n_M is the Manning roughness coefficient for the channel material, A is the cross-sectional area of flow through the channel, R is the hydraulic radius of channel, and S is the slope of the channel. Hydraulic radius is described by equation 4.2.2 below

$$R = A/P_w \quad (4.2.2)$$

where P_w is the wetted perimeter of the conduit.

SWMM does not track dispersion, treating the network as a series of plug flows. This results in higher peak flowrates with periods of no flow that would not be encountered in actual sewers.

While SWMM does account for atmospheric temperature when determining inflows due to snow melt or losses due to evaporation, it does not natively track the temperature of wastewater itself. However, as SWMM does track pollutant concentrations in wastewater a simple model of wastewater temperature could be created by treating it as a material pollutant in an otherwise homogenous flow. SWMM ignores diffusion of pollutants, instead treating them as a slug.

In a simple case of two flows (F_1, T_1 , F_2, T_2) with different temperatures (T_1, T_2) mixing at a junction node (as illustrated right in Figure 4.2.1), the temperature of wastewater leaving that junction node (T_3) would be described by equation 4.2.3 below

$$T_3 = \frac{T_1 F_1 + T_2 F_2}{F_1 + F_2} \quad (4.2.3)$$

In general, this takes the form shown below in equation 4.2.4 for a confluence of n pipes.

$$T_{mix} = \frac{T_1 F_1 + T_2 F_2 + \dots + T_n F_n}{\sum F_n} \quad (4.2.4)$$

where T_{mix} is the temperature of the resultant flow.

Pollutants can be removed from any node in the network using a treatment function which takes the form of an equation describing either the outlet concentration or removal fraction from that node. Depth of wastewater, flowrate, surface area, simulation time step, and hydraulic residence time at the node are all valid variables for removal expressions.

Figure 4.2.1
Example of
mixing flow at
junction

5. Methodology

5.1 Overview of Workflow

Figure 5.1.1 below gives an overview of the workflow used during this project. Data from the UK Time Use Survey, UK household occupancy statistics, and survey of UK appliance ownership (penetration) were required to generate water demand profiles for households in SIMDEUM.

5.2 Collection of Data Required for SIMDEUM

By examining the plans for the Brabazon development, the seven types of housing listed below in Table 5.2.1 were identified with their differentiating features

Type	Social/Private	Bedrooms	Ensuite Shower Rooms	Integrated white goods
1	Social	2	0	No
2	Social	3	0	No
3	Private	2	1	Yes
4	Private	3	1	Yes
5	Private	4	1	Yes
6	Private	4	2	Yes
7	Private	1.606*	0.606*	Yes

Type 7 housing was an attempt to estimate the average household type in the Navigator apartment building which contained both one- and two-bedroom apartments in a 13:20 ratio.

Demographic data from ONS (2017) provided data for household occupancy in the South West of England by number of bedrooms and tenure type. For social housing units, only the tenure type “social rented” was considered while for other housing units all available data was used. For the purposes of finding the average occupancy it was assumed that households listed as containing 6 or more occupants held 6 occupants only as no further information was available. For finding the percentage of households that fell within the SIMDEUM “family” category, any household with three or more occupants was counted. When assigning average occupancy and occupancy category type for type 7 households, a 13:20 weighted average of one bedroom and two-bedroom households was used.

The necessary values for diurnal patterns were derived from the United Kingdom Time Use Survey (Gershuny and Sullivan, 2017). The survey broke down the day into ten-minute intervals and for each demographic group the fraction of respondents who reported being either asleep or away from home was found.

Max sleep	Time		
0.95	03:50:00		
Min sleep	Time		
0.01	12:00:00		
Range	Mid Point	Lower SD bound	Upper SD bound
0.94	0.48	0.33	0.65

Figure 5.2.1 Example Excel sheet for finding what values to find using VLOOKUP for averages and SDs.

The average time of getting up was defined as the earliest instance at which the midpoint between the maximum and minimum fraction of respondents reported being awake. The estimated average time was made more precise by interpolating

between ten-minute intervals. Standard deviations (SD) were found by looking for the time at which 34.1% and 68.2% of the range was reached and interpolating as before. This resulted in two standard deviation values which were asymmetrical, so these were averaged for the purposes of use in SIMDEUM as shown in Figure 5.2.2. The average time of leaving the house was defined and found in the same way, using the fraction of respondents not at home.

<68% Wake	Fraction sleep	>68% Wake	Fraction sleep	68% Wake	SD
07:40:00	0.36	07:50:00	0.31	07:46:34	00:32:18
<50% Wake	Fraction sleep	>50% Wake	Fraction sleep	50% Wake	Average SD
07:10:00	0.49	07:20:00	0.46	07:14:16	00:27:42
<34% Wake	Fraction sleep	>34% Wake	Fraction sleep	34% Wake	SD
06:50:00	0.67	07:00:00	0.52	06:51:09	00:23:06

Figure 5.2.2 Example Excel sheet showing interpolation for average waking time and symmetrical SD.

To find the average durations sleeping and away from home for each demographic, the average times of returning home and going to bed were found by the same method used to find times of waking and departure from the home. The intervals between average times of leaving and returning were taken as the average duration away, with the standard deviation being found only by considering the variation in the time of return. Figure 5.2.3 below gives an impression of this.

Min away	Time				
0.05	04:10:00				
Max away	Time				
0.47	11:20:00				
Range	Midpoint	Lower SD bound	Upper SD bound		
0.42	0.26	0.19	0.33		
<50% Leave	Fraction away	>50% Leave	Fraction away	50% Leave	
09:10:00	0.24	09:20:00	0.27	09:16:44	
<50% Return	Fraction away	>50% Return	Fraction away	50% Return	Duration
16:40:00	0.27	16:50:00	0.26	16:49:05	07:32:22
<68% Return	Fraction away	>68% Return	Fraction away	68% Return	Time from midpoint
17:40:00	0.19	17:50:00	0.19	17:45:37	00:56:32
<34% Return	Fraction away	>34% Return	Fraction away	34% Return	Time from midpoint
15:50:00	0.35	16:00:00	0.32	15:55:58	00:53:07
					Avg. time from midpoint
					00:54:49

Figure 5.2.3 Example spreadsheet showing how time away from home was found.

Except for social housing, penetration values for taps, washing machines, and other appliances were obtained from private correspondence with the developer as the properties are being finished with white goods included. For social housing the penetration values for dishwashers and washing machines were taken from BRE (2013) which provided values by size of household. Although the values from BRE (2013) are a decade old at time of writing and the total penetration of appliances continues to increase, the lower rates of penetration in social housing overall may compensate for this discrepancy: as of 2011 only 19% of social housing households had a dishwasher versus 40% in the total population (BRE, 2013, p.14).

Due to lack of readily available data for the UK, the values for water usage for each installation type were taken from the demo files packaged with SIMDEUM which are calibrated for the Dutch context. The only modification made at this stage was to decrease the shaving frequency

for additional bathroom taps from average to low as these appliances were not associated with a proper bathroom and therefore unlikely to be used for shaving. Once the necessary data had been collected they were compiled into an .spg file for use by SIMDEUM using the Watershare Tool.

5.3 Modifying SWMM

Figure 5.3.1 below shows the SWMM model as was inherited from Hofman (2021) at the start of this project, with information of channel size, roughness and slope already provided. As the viability of WWHR systems is usually defined in terms of dry weather flow conditions, all that was required at this stage was to link each inflow node to a flow and temperature time series produced by SIMDEUM for the associated housing type.

The apartment block at the node labelled as 4. in Figure 5.3.1 above contained 33 units: 13 one-bedroom units, and 20 two-bedroom units with ensuite bathrooms. Ten additional inflow nodes were later added to the network as SWMM as shown in Figure 5.3.2 (left) only accommodates one flow pattern per node, with each node being given a flow scale factor of 3.3.

To connect the new nodes to the network at node 4, ten new conduits were created with a length of 1m. The channel dimensions, slope, and roughness for the conduits connecting the new nodes to the network were the same as those of the conduit connecting the original node 4. to the wider network. The original conduit connecting node 4. to the wider network was shortened by 1m to compensate for the length of the new conduits.

For attempting to prove the viability of using SWMM's pollutant removal function to model temperature loss through the network the following removal equation 5.3.1 was used

$$T_{outlet} = T_{inlet} * \exp(0.01DT) \quad (5.3.1)$$

where DT was the simulation time step.

5.4 Potential Heat Recovery

The potentially recoverable power (Q_{PR}) at a given time interval was estimated from the product of the wastewater flowrate (F_w), specific heat capacity and density of wastewater (c and ρ_{ww}), and the change in water temperature taking place due to the heat exchanger (ΔT_{HX}) as shown below in equation (5.4.1)

$$Q_{PR} = F_w \cdot c \cdot \Delta T_{HX} \cdot \rho_{ww} \quad (5.4.1)$$

The specific heat capacity was taken as $4.18 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and the density of wastewater was assumed to be 1000 kg m^{-3} based on Funamizu et al. (2001), and the change in wastewater temperature due to heat exchange was the elevated temperature above 15.2°C capped to a maximum value of either 0.5°C to ensure no impact on downstream WWTPs, 2°C following the specifications given by Huber (2021), or 3°C as an optimistic best case scenario with current technology given by Ali and Gillich (2019). 15.2°C was chosen as the reference point as this was the value given by the Energy Savings Trust (2008, p.26) for the average main's water temperature in the UK and it is assumed that heat transfer from wastewater would be poor beneath this temperature. When total recoverable energy was desired then Q_{PR} was multiplied by the size of the time step in the simulation which was normally five minutes.

As many more appliances were added to households than were found present in any of the demo files packaged with the SIMDEUM software it was decided to investigate the impact of device frequency. This was done by creating new .spg files for type-6 houses, dividing the original appliance frequency of toilets, bathroom taps, and showers by the number of those appliances present in the house (i.e. 4,4, and 3 respectively), and measuring the impact on flowrates and temperatures around node 1. on Figure 5.3.1. For bathroom taps the frequency of shaving was

restored to “average” for each tap as otherwise the frequency of shaving would have been adjusted down by too much. This modification allowed for multiple showers to be in use at a single time, which could result in higher overall usage as each device has an independent minimum time between two uses (offset) but not to the same degree as multiple copies of an appliance would – importantly for the hydraulic model in general it allowed for higher peak discharge. Files for discharge patterns were selected to ensure that the same number of occupants (11) were present in both the original and reduced frequency scenario.

6. Results

6.1 Diurnal Patterns

Shown below in Figures 6.1.1 and 6.1.2 are the diurnal patterns for the relevant demographic groups recognised by the UK Time Use Survey data. A working adult in SIMDEUM is defined as an adult who works more than 20 hours a week.

Figure 6.1.2 Diurnal patterns for adult cohorts

6.2 Household Composition

Figure 6.2.1 Proportion of SIMDEUM household types for all housing (left), social housing (centre), and private housing (right).

	1 Bedroom	2 Bedrooms	3 Bedrooms	4 Bedrooms
All	1.31 \pm 0.59	1.86 \pm 0.90	2.45 \pm 1.20	2.88 \pm 1.30
Private	1.36 \pm 0.63	1.81 \pm 0.85	2.38 \pm 1.15	2.85 \pm 1.28
Social	1.22 \pm 0.51	2.18 \pm 1.11	3.07 \pm 1.58	4.00 \pm 1.98

6.3 Discharge Patterns

Figure 6.3.1 below shows the flowrate at the network outfall, with the standard deviation of the five day average. An average of 16000L were discharged into the network each day and the flowrate failed to meet the industry recommended 600LPM.

Figure 6.3.1 Flowrate at network outfall for **one weekday**, averaged over five simulations with the area in grey representing one standard deviation either side of the average.

Figure 6.3.2 below shows the temperature of the wastewater in excess of 15.2, temperature met target 55.6% of the time.

Figure 6.3.2 Temperature at network outfall for one weekday, averaged over five simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.3.3 Inflow at node 1, averaged over five days with original and reduced appliance frequencies.

Figure 6.3.3 above shows inflow at node 1. over a 24 hour period averaged over five days at the original appliance frequency and the reduced device frequency discussed earlier. Total inflow was found as shown in Table 6.3.1 below.

Table 6.3.1 Total Inflow Through Node 1. Over One Day With Original and Reduced Appliance Frequencies		
Appliance Frequency	Total Inflow [L]	Total Inflow Per Person [L]
Original	960	87
Reduced	638	58

6.4 Effect of Averaging on Simulation

Figure 6.4.1 Flowrate from apartment block for one weekday using a single node with scale factor of 33, averaged over five simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.2 Temperature from apartment block for one weekday using a single node with scale factor of 33, averaged over five simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.3. Flowrate from apartment block for one weekday using ten nodes with scale factor of 3.3, averaged over five simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.4 Temperature from apartment block for one weekday using 10 nodes with scale factor of 3.3, averaged over five simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.5 Flowrate from apartment block for one weekday using ten nodes with scale factor of 3.3, averaged over 50 simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.6 Temperature from apartment block for one weekday using 10 nodes with scale factor of 3.3, averaged over 50 simulations with boundaries of standard deviation shown.

Figure 6.4.7. Average ratio of standard deviation to temperature/flowrate value for apartment building outflow (10 nodes) over a variable number of simulations.

6.5 Demonstration of Heat Losses

Figure 6.5.1 shows excess temperature at network outfall (node 3 on Figure 5.3.1) averaged over five simulations, showing the effect of implementing temperature losses.

Figure 6.5.2 shows excess temperature at node 2 on Figure 5.3.1 averaged over five simulations, showing the effect of implementing temperature losses.

6.7 Recoverable Heat

Figure 6.7.1 below shows the maximum potential power recovery at the network outfall averaged over five days, under three assumptions of maximum cooling.

Figure 6.7.1 Potential recovered power at network outfall averaged over five days under three different assumptions of maximum useful cooling.

Figure 6.7.2 Potential recovered power at network outfall against water heating demand from Intertek (2012).

Table 6.7.1 Potentially Recoverable Thermal Energy at Network Outfall			
Useful Cooling	0.5°C	2°C	3°C
Potential Recovery [MJ/day]	32.8	127.9	189.8

7. Discussion

The simulation produced satisfactory diurnal patterns that mirror results seen in sewers elsewhere: an initial peak following the morning followed by a lull due to people leaving their homes, followed by a more extended period of high flow in the evening. This can be seen in Figure 6.7.2 where heating demand precedes available power, although there is a base load not accounted for in this curve.

Assuming an average occupancy of 2.4 for the 113 housing units modelled the total flow per person was approximately 60 litres per day. When examining the node 1. with a known number of upstream occupants, the average daily discharge was found to be 87 litres per person, which is 58% of the 150L UK average and still only 70% of the new build targets of the 2010 Building Regulations (Aquaterra, 2010). This is surprising given how many appliances were in the type 6 housing upstream of node 1. and may be due to the model's use of European values for water usage which are on average lower than those in the UK (ibid.). Reducing the appliance frequency of type 6 housing in proportion to the additional appliances led to an average 33.5% reduction in discharge to sewers, which suggests that the SIMDEUM model handles additional appliances well if they are of the same type.

Minimum flowrate for in-sewer WWHR systems not reached with maximum flowrates in the region of 24LPM compared to the minimum of 600LPM recommended by manufacturers, suggesting that any heat recovery station should be located further downstream. This is not surprising as Osterholt and Hofman (2015) found that WWHR wasn't well suited for small housing projects of 50 homes and the first stage of the Brabazon development is not much larger. However, Hrabová, Hrdlička, and Tlašek (2019) note that in-sewer WWHR systems may be viable even on scales as small as 10kW, which is only twice what was obtained at the network outfall under the assumption of 3°C during peak times. If the flowrates have been underestimated by a factor of 2-3 as discussed previously, a 10kW WWHR system may be viable with adequate storage for heat recovered during peak times. Furthermore, as the heat recovery station can be sited within 500m of the network outfall tested, this leaves open the possibility of including the region as part of a wider district heating system.

Increasing the number of simulations over which the results were averaged from 5 to 10 considerably decreased the standard deviation of the flow pattern, but further increases had diminishing effects. This shows the strength of the model when operated at this scale.

8. Future Work

8.1 Data Collection

Much of the data used in this report will soon be able to be updated due to the 2021 census. Specifically, washing machine penetration and household occupancy can be updated shortly. Diurnal patterns for weekends can be found using the same dataset as was used to find weekday patterns and should be used to give a more accurate picture of flow patterns.

There are still some discrepancies between the demographic groups used within the SIMDEUM and those in the data collected by ONS which might be useful to resolve, but these are a minor concern relating to the definition of children aged 17-21.

8.2 SIMDEUM

Updating the frequency of appliance usage is a high priority as demonstrated by the four household test case, but more research will be required to find how additional appliances change the frequency of use in real cases. As Blokker (2017) advises, it would be wise to update other demand to match the British context as the system was calibrated around Dutch water usage.

Currently there is an issue with how SIMDEUM handles washing machine cycles that start near the end of a simulated timespan, causing the simulation to fail. The likelihood of encountering this error increases with the number of days and houses simulated, which limits the tool's ease of use.

SIMDEUM does not generate single parent households or households made of more than two adults with no children, with single parent households accounting for 14.9% of family households (ONS, 2019).

SIMDEUM cannot switch between weekday and weekend demand patterns. Although it is possible to combine the output created by two different demand patterns there will be slight inconsistencies due to the randomly generated household composition so that a house that is simulated as having four occupants during the week would only have one at a weekend or vice versa.

8.3 SWMM

Temperature losses as modelled thus far should be taken only as a proof of concept of what is possible within the SWMM program. Were SWMM to be used in this way over competing software such as TEMPEST, proper calibration would be required.

In Abdel-Aal's 2015 thesis he develops a steady state model of sewer temperature that considered heat losses through conduction to the pipe wall into the surrounding soil as well as heat losses to the air in the sewer through convection. The system boundary of this model is shown below in Figure 8.3.1, where d_p is the thickness of the pipe wall, D is the inner pipe diameter, h is the depth of wastewater, B is the free surface width, d_s is the distance to ambient soil temperature from the pipe wall, q_{wa} is the per unit length heat transfer from wastewater to sewer air, and q_{ws} is the per unit length heat transfer from wastewater to the surrounding soil.

Figure 8.3.1. Diagram of heat losses through cross-section of pipe from Abdel-Aal (2015, p.26).

Assuming a constant mass flow rate across a given interval the two sources of heat loss were simplified by Abdel-Aal (2015) as follows in equation 8.3.1 and 8.3.2 below

$$q'_{wa} = \frac{T_w - T_a}{R_{wa}} \quad (8.3.1)$$

$$q'_{ws} = \frac{T_w - T_s}{R_{ws}} \quad (8.3.2)$$

Where q' is heat transfer per unit length, T_w is the temperature of wastewater, T_a is the temperature of sewer air, T_s is the ambient temperature of soil at d_s , and R is the thermal resistivity governing the associated heat transfer.

By assuming a non-slip boundary condition at the pipe wall, Abdel-Aal (2015) was able to ignore convective heat transfer from the wastewater to the soil leaving conduction as the only

consideration: conduction through the thickness of the pipe wall, and conduction through d_s . This is shown in equation 8.3.3 below

$$R_{ws} = \frac{d_p}{k_p P_w} + \frac{d_s}{k_s P_w} \quad (8.3.3)$$

where k_p is the thermal conductivity of the pipe and k_s is the thermal conductivity of the soil. Busby (2016) provides values for the median thermal conductivity of the three major soil types found in UK (shown below in Table 8.3.1) and these values could be embedded into SWMM for other users to reference.

Type	Thermal Conductivity [Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	Thermal Diffusivity [m ² s ⁻¹]	Specific Heat Capacity [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	Density [kg m ⁻³]
Sandy	1.56	0.9961	1415	1760
Loam	1.15	0.7173	1014	1980
Clay	1.81	1.0295×10 ⁻⁶	986	1818

Thermal resistivity to heat transfer between wastewater and sewer air

$$R_{wa} = \frac{1}{B h_{wa}} \quad (8.3.4)$$

Where h_{wa} is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the wastewater and air. h_{wa} was found to be a function of sewer airspeed (u_a) and wastewater mean velocity (u_w) as given below in equation 8.3.5 (Abdel-Aal, 2015, p.28)

$$h_{wa} = 5.85 \times \sqrt{|u_a - u_w|} \quad (8.3.5)$$

Qian et al. (2020) recommend a series of empirical relations to find average air speed in sewer pipe (u_a) using the surface width of wastewater flow (B), the unwetted perimeter of pipe (P_u), and the average speed of wastewater (u_w) at that point, the simplest of which is given below as equation 8.3.6

$$u_a = 0.682 B u_w / P_u \quad (8.3.6)$$

Assuming circular pipe geometry as shown in Figure 8.3.2 (left) allows us to find B using the depth of water (h) which is already tracked in SWMM and the pipe diameter (D) as seen in equation 8.3.7 and 8.3.8 below

$$B = D \sin(\theta/2) \quad (8.3.7)$$

$$\theta = 2 \arccos\left(\frac{D-2h}{D}\right) \quad (8.3.8)$$

More difficulty will arise in attempting to find the unwetted perimeter as the equation changes if the pipe is filled past its midpoint as shown in the conditional expression 8.3.9 below

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } 2h > D, \quad P_u &= \pi D - D\theta/2 \\ \text{if } 2h < D, \quad P_u &= D\theta/2 \end{aligned} \quad (8.3.9)$$

This could be modelled in SWMM using the recognised step(x) function, which returns a zero where $x \leq 0$. The form this might take is shown below in equation 8.3.10 but the variables would need to be changed for implementation in SWMM

$$P_u = \text{step}(2h - D) * (\pi D - D\theta/2) + \text{step}(D - 2h) * (D\theta/2) \quad (8.3.10)$$

Finally for this method, u_w can be found by dividing the volumetric flowrate by the area of flow which is a segment given by D and θ as given below in 8.3.11 and 8.3.12 for radians (which SWMM uses by default)

$$u_w = \frac{F_w}{A} \quad (8.3.11)$$

$$A = \frac{D^2(\theta - \sin \theta)}{8} \quad (8.3.12)$$

Alternatively, Abdel-Aal (2015, p.28), found that taking u_a to be $2-3\text{ms}^{-1}$ greater than u_w gave satisfactory results in his simulation. Whichever method is used to find u_a , h_{wa} may be found with equation 8.3.5 using B as calculated in equation 8.3.7.

Under the steady state assumption and other simplifications made by Abdel-Aal (2015) we arrive at the following energy balance between two nodes

$$\rho F_w c_p (T_n - T_{n+1}) = \Delta L \times (q'_{wa} + q'_{ws}) \quad (8.3.13)$$

where T_n is the temperature at node n , T_{n+1} is the temperature of wastewater leaving node n as it arrives at node $n+1$ and ΔL is the distance between the two nodes. Rearrangement and

substitution of equation 8.3.1 and 8.3.2 gives the following expression for the temperature one node downstream of a known position (Abdel-Aal, 2015, p.29)

$$T_{n+1} = T_n - \Delta L \times \left(\frac{R_{wa}^{-1} \times (T_n - T_a) + R_{ws}^{-1} \times (T_n - T_s)}{\rho F_w c_p} \right) \tag{8.3.14}$$

where T_n is the temperature at node n, T_{n+1} is the temperature of wastewater leaving node n as it arrives at node n+1 and ΔL is the distance between the two nodes. Note that this scheme would not work for a stream that splits into multiple channels, but these are not usually found in gravity drained sewers.

As SWMM has a universal atmospheric temperature variable, it may be possible to include sewer air temperature in a more sophisticated model of temperature loss although no way has yet been found to call atmospheric temperature time series in a pollutant removal expression. A soil temperature time series would also be useful for longer simulations, but as ground temperatures at the depth of sewer pipes do not show as much daily variance it would not be as useful to include. Furthermore Abdel-Aal et al. (2014) found that aside from upstream wastewater temperatures the most important factor for predicting wastewater temperature at a given point is the sewer air temperature, so complex considerations of soil condition are of a lower priority.

In Figure 8.3.3 below a simplified form of equation 8.3.14 has been implemented into SWMM, removing the terms governing heat losses to soil ($R_{ws}^{-1} \times (T_n - T_s)$) for simplicity, substituting in equation 8.3.5, 8.3.6, 8.3.7 and 8.3.8 to find R_{wa}^{-1}

Pollutant	Treatment Expression
Temperature	C= Temperature - (22.6)*(Temperature-10)/(0.15*sin(2*acos((0.15-2*DEPTH)/0.15))*5.85*2.5^(0.5)*4.18*FLOW)

Figure 8.3.3 Example temperature loss equation in SWMM for constant air temperature with losses to soil ignored.

T_a has been replaced with a constant value of 10°C as it has not yet been possible to include a time series, the ρV terms have disappeared because the flowrate is given in LPS, pipe diameter has been taken as 0.15m, and ΔL is given as 22.6m. Currently, the angle θ must be recalculated each time it is used which quickly produces unwieldy expressions but the use of the step(x) function to find P_u as in equation 8.3.10 has been tested and returns no errors.

8.4 Summary

The highest priorities for further development are implementing appliance frequency reductions for pattern generation and finding a way to call a time series or a customised function in the temperature “pollutant” removal expressions in SWMM.

9. Conclusions

The model produces results that follow expected patterns for diurnal flow but underestimates flowrates by a factor of 2-3. If these faults are corrected the Brabazon development may appear to be a promising candidate for small scale WWHR systems, particularly as the site expands.

SWMM shows great potential for modelling temperature in sewer networks through adaptation of its pollutant function, although minor modifications may be necessary to make this capability more accessible.

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